

CV MNEMONIC: ENCODING NUMERIC CODES FOR DIGITAL USABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The authors present a general mnemonic technique, the Consonant-Vowel (CV) Mnemonic method, to map hard-to-recall numeric codes to pronounceable strings consisting of consonant-vowel pairs. The mnemonic codes generated in this manner are pronounceable and generally easier to remember than their corresponding numeric code. The use of CV Mnemonic codes can potentially limit errors that accompany numeric entry by humans in digital systems, thereby improving usability. We compare the CV Mnemonic method to well-known mnemonic schemes used to encode numbers, such as the phonetic method, the phoneword mnemonic, and the table-index method. We also discuss potential CV Mnemonic applications in improving the usability of digital environments in marketing communication and user validation interfaces.

Keywords: digital mnemonics, digital usability, consonant-vowel mnemonic

INTRODUCTION

Numeric codes are frequently used to augment security in digital environments. Such numeric codes comprise relatively short numeric codes such as PINs and two-factor authentication codes and lengthier codes such as credit card numbers, encryption keys, and digital wallet account numbers. Users are commonly required to recall or recognize such machine or user-generated codes while using digital systems. These requirements can sometimes be onerous for users. Even individuals accustomed to memorizing a large number of words may struggle with recalling numeric codes. For example, taxonomists who can memorize many taxon names may struggle with 4-digit pin codes (Lücking 2019). Individuals with cognitive limitations, may struggle extensively with the appropriate use of numeric codes while accessing digital systems (e.g., Sandberg et al. 2021). Consequently, the ubiquitous use of numeric codes can hamper usability in digital environments.

This paper proposes a simple and general approach called Consonant-Vowel (CV) Mnemonic, which transforms any k-digit numeric code to a pronounceable k-character alphabetic code, consisting of consonant-vowel pairs, that is generally more memorable than the original numeric code. For example, we can transform 16-digit credit card number into a 16-character alphabetic code consisting of a sequence of consonant-vowel pairs, such as:

17 88 93 30 33 31 33 44 → ME MO RA BI LI TE CO DE

The rationale for the extensive use of numeric codes lies in making digital systems more secure. Such codes are typically hard-to-guess by unauthorized humans and machines. However, the security gained from using numeric codes, such as PINs, often comes at the cost of usability (Adams and Sasse 1999; Topakara et al. 2007). Moreover, the inability to recall or recognize such numeric codes accurately can potentially impair digital usability by inducing delays or errors.

Such errors and delays may result in significant adverse consequences for the user. Difficulty in remembering codes can endanger users' security, such as when they lock themselves out of their phone or bank account because of wrong or delayed entry. Similarly, not recognizing the entry of a wrong account number while filing an IT refund can lead to loss or delay in receiving such payments.¹

MNEMONICS FOR IMPROVING USABILITY OF NUMERIC CODES

Given the link between the memorability of numeric codes and digital usability, users will benefit from a general way of representing such numeric codes in a way that is recalled and recognized easily. One potential solution involves the use of mnemonics (or mnemonic devices), which are techniques used to assist and improve memory (Yates 1966; Bellezza 1991; Dickel 1983; Worthen and Hunt 2011). Studies demonstrate that mnemonics can be effective in improving users' memory in digital environments (e.g., Nelson and Vu 2010; Vetter et al. 2020). Our interest is in mnemonic methods that can help users remember numbers. Popular mnemonic techniques for encoding numbers include the phonetic method (Higbee 1977; Patton and Lantzy 1987), the telephone mnemonic (Horky 1995), and the table-index method (Kusnick 1999).

CV MNEMONIC MAPPING SCHEME

We propose that CV Mnemonic can potentially enhance digital usability in situations that require memorizing numeric codes by encoding the numbers as pronounceable consonant-vowel sequences. The CV Mnemonic method involves a pronounceable mapping from the numeric domain to the alphabetic CV domain, with a mapping scheme where two-digit numbers from 00 to 99 are associated with a unique consonant-vowel combination. 100! distinct mapping schemes from the numeric domain to the CV domain are possible. We can also define specific standard mapping schemes that can be easy to generate or remember. We refer to the default mapping as the canonical mapping (Table 1). As an example, we provide an illustrative mapping where numeric codes are replaced by CV combinations as depicted in the table. We refer to this mapping as the *balanced mapping* scheme, from the numerical sequence to the CV Mnemonic, is depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Balanced Mapping of the CV Mnemonic

00 BA	01 BE	02 BI	03 BO	04 BU	05 CA	06 CE	07 CI	08 CO	09 CU
10 DA	11 DE	12 DI	13 DO	14 DU	15 FA	16 FE	17 FI	18 FO	19 FU
20 GA	21 GE	22 GI	23 GO	24 GU	25 HA	26 HE	27 HI	28 HO	29 HU
30 JA	31 JE	32 JI	33 JO	34 JU	35 KA	36 KE	37 KI	38 KO	39 KU
40 LA	41 LE	42 LI	43 LO	44 LU	45 MA	46 ME	47 MI	48 MO	49 MU
50 NA	51 NE	52 NI	53 NO	54 NU	55 PA	56 PE	57 PI	58 PO	59 PU
60 QA	61 QE	62 QI	63 QO	64 QU	65 RA	66 RE	67 RI	68 RO	69 RU
70 SA	71 SE	72 SI	73 SO	74 SU	75 TA	76 TE	77 TI	78 TO	79 TU
80 VA	81 VE	82 VI	83 VO	84 VU	85 WA	86 WE	87 WI	88 WO	89 WU
90 YA	91 YE	92 YI	93 YO	94 YU	95 ZA	96 ZE	97 ZI	98 ZO	99 ZU

The balanced mapping scheme encodes the numeric code '4000 1234 5678 9010' as the CV Mnemonic code, 'LABA DIJU PETO YADA,' which is more pronounceable than the original

¹ See: <https://www.irs.gov/faqs/irs-procedures/refund-inquiries/refund-inquiries-18> (accessed on March 19, 2021)

numeric code. In the following sections, we illustrate different applications where the use of CV Mnemonic can improve usability of codes in the context of marketing communication and user-validation interfaces.

MARKETING COMMUNICATION

Sundry forms of mnemonics have been used to make marketing information memorable. Mnemonics have also been suggested as a potential pedagogical tool in marketing (Malhotra 1991).² Mnemonics in marketing include musical mnemonic and numeric mnemonics. Musical mnemonics have been used in advertising for communicating slogans (e.g., Yalch 1991). The use of mnemonics in radio advertising in the form of rhymes have shown to improve brand recall (Smith and Philips 2001).

A well-known application of numeric-mnemonics is in communicating numeric marketing information such as phone numbers, coupon codes and products in a form that can be recognized or recalled by customers. This benefit of number mnemonics in marketing communication is exemplified by success of encoding phone numbers in advertising in the form of phone-words or telephone mnemonics (e.g., Topolinski 2011). In the past, 1800-numbers could be encoded with characters that represents its overlapping location on the phone number pad. Thus, 1-800 numbers in the US such as 1-800-DOMINOS and 1-800-FLOWERS became an important part of US television advertising and a source of cultural motifs, particular in the latter part of the 1900s prior to the advent of the mobile phone era (e.g., McKinney 1999). Such codes were found to be important brand resources and worthy of trademark protection (e.g., Monahan 1997). Beyond advertising, phone-words have also served as vanity numbers in other forms of marketing communication. Corporate companies may still use telephone mnemonics in selecting allocating phone numbers for customer interactions. Another example of the use of numeric mnemonics in advertising can be found in Japan, where telephone numbers are also printed using katakana, hiragana or kanji characters with phonological elements that correspond to the telephone number sequence (Schourup 2000).

A significant drawback of the telephone mnemonic is that not all codes can be converted to mnemonic alphabetic codes. While converting a memorable word or phrase to a numeric code is easily accomplished, the reverse problem of converting a given number to a mnemonic is problematic, since not all numeric codes map on to memorable phone words. In contrast, CV Mnemonic can be used to encode any numeric code. Thus, providing contact information in the form of CV Mnemonic may be an effective solution where system-generated or random numbers have to be converted to mnemonic codes.

Figure 1: CV Mnemonic as Product Codes for Marketing

Nike Varsity Compete TR 2 Cool
Grey/Black/Dark Grey 7

\$95

UPC: 192499682970
UPC CVM: FUGU ZURO HUSA
Text FUGU ZURO HUSA to 8808

² 4Ps is possibly the most well-known pedagogical mnemonic.

One such potential application of the CV Mnemonic lies in encoding serially or randomly generated product codes for use in marketing communication alongside or in place of product numbers. For example, an ad may display both the 12-digit UPC code of the product, as well as the equivalent mnemonic (Figure 1). The higher pronounceability of CV Mnemonic can potentially allow users to both recall and recognize the product.³ Similarly, CV Mnemonic can also potentially be used to generate personalized mnemonic coupon codes.⁴

USER-VALIDATION INTERFACES

CV Mnemonic finds applications in situations that call for the customer inputting a numeric code as part of a validation process. Depending on the context, the user may have to recall the code or hold part of the code in working memory as they transfer the code from one media to another. In such situation, usability is enhanced if the speed of transferring the code, as well as human-errors are reduced. Some context requires users to hold numeric codes in their memory for longer periods of time.⁵ Recall of these codes may be improved if the codes are encoded as a CV Mnemonic. One such application involves Personal Identification Numbers (PINs) which are used to secure Banking transactions, home security and mobile devices.⁶ PIN codes are generally more secure if they are random numbers, such as when auto-generated by a computer. However, even randomly generated 4-digit PINs may be hard for users to recall (Lücking 2019). The inability to recall PIN codes may result in consequences ranging from inconvenient delays to serious security risks. If the PIN code is not recalled on an iPhone, the users can potentially lose their data.⁷ The use of mnemonics can potentially improve recall. In home security systems, a telephone pad with phone mnemonic is provided. However, as described earlier, the telephone mnemonic scheme is unsuitable for converting system generated random numbers into mnemonic codes.

Figure 2: ISO/IEC 9995-8 Phoneword Scheme and CV Mnemonic Numpad

³ Similar applications include using CVM codes in billboards, online advertising. Also, CV Mnemonic as audio QR code where the user can generate a pronounceable CV code (similar to bitly or goo.gl) and this can be the link for a website. This can be in the form of `cvm.fyi/PARAMOSA`, which will generate a link to the web page of interest.

⁴ The use of generic coupon codes or discount such as OFFER2020 may be considered a gimmick. Making the codes personalized or complex, can decrease the memorability of the code. The use of CV Mnemonics offers a potential third way, where non-generic, yet-memorable coupon codes can be generated with ease.

⁵ Another example is brain wallets.

⁶ Principles of PIN management are described by the ISO 9564 standards.

⁷ <https://support.apple.com/en-us/HT204306>; Also See:

<https://tidbits.com/2018/01/15/what-to-do-if-your-ipad-gets-disabled-by-too-many-passcode-entries/>

For such an application a modified keypad design to generate CV Mnemonic codes might be implemented (Figure 2). Alternatively, the users can use a software application to convert the CV Mnemonic to the numeric PIN. Similarly, individuals are often required to recall system-generated or serially generated numeric codes such as Social Security Numbers, Employee ID numbers, and student ID numbers for the purpose of validating their identity. These numeric codes are typically system-generated codes, i.e., the users do not have the option of choosing a unique ID number for themselves. This implies that the telephone mnemonic scheme is not useful. The use of CV Mnemonics can potentially make such codes easier to retrieve or can substitute for such codes. For example, CV Mnemonic can be used to provide a mnemonic substitute for identifiers defined under International Standard Name Identifier (ISIN) described in ISO 27729.⁸

CV Mnemonic can also improve usability in customer information validation interfaces where the user does not memorize a code but must read and input a long numeric code. In such situations, users are required to hold in working memory a numeric code (often part of a longer code) for a short duration. The use of CV Mnemonic can potentially improve both the speed of input and reduce errors. For example, as part of two-factor authentication, users are required to transfer a code from one device, such as a mobile device, to another, such as a personal computer. Such authentication systems require users to hold at least a part of the code in memory at least for a brief period while transferring the code from one device to other, adversely impacting usability.

Figure 3: CVM Authentication Codes

⁸ <https://isni.org/>. Such identification schemes might allow the possibility of vanity mnemonic identifiers.

We propose that some users may find it easier to transfer CV Mnemonic codes rather than a numeric code, given that it is more pronounceable compared to numeric sequences. In such cases, authentication systems can potentially improve usability by sending users both numeric and CV Mnemonic codes (Figure 3). A similar application can be demonstrated in the case of payment card The CV Mnemonic may be also be printed on payment cards as an alternate way of representing the card number (Figure 4).

Figure 4: CV Mnemonic in Payment Cards

There are two benefits of displaying the CV Mnemonic code alongside the card number: (1) It can serve as a mnemonic replacement for the numeric code, and (2) it can be used to error check the numeric code. CV Mnemonic can serve as a replacement for numeric codes since it can potentially increase the speed as well as accuracy entry of credit card information easier for users. Often users are required to input their credit card numbers when using digital systems, such as online shopping. While the codes may be stored in a locally or remotely for later retrieval, some users might be inclined to enter the number manually. In situations which require users to type the code, users may find it easier to input the mnemonic code quickly and accurately, given that it more pronounceable than the numeric code.

Second, the CV Mnemonic can be used to error-check the numeric code. Users of digital systems are sometimes required to confirm or verify numeric codes by typing the codes a second time. For example, a user providing credit card information on a payment service may be asked to type the credit card number twice (Figure 5). The benefit of such a repetition is that it allows the system to detect errors generated by mistyping codes by comparing the two codes. However, if the form of error is systematic, such as transposition of adjacent digits or reading multiple digits that repeat wrongly, the user may commit the same error a second time. The requirement to repeat the code is inconvenient to the user, and commonly users often copy and paste the code. This action can be partly prevented by locking the first code from being copied; however, the need to type a long numeric code may be perceived as onerous by users.

Figure 5: CV Mnemonic used as a confirmation code

Credit Card Information

Mnemonic Code

PEZI ZIJI RIYI WORU

Credit Card Number

5697 9732 6792 8869

Exp Date Security Code

MM/YY XXX

We propose two different approaches where the CV Mnemonic can be used to verify the code without hampering usability. For both these approaches, we assume that the user has immediate access to both the numeric code and CV Mnemonic. In the first approach, a user is asked to type in both formats. One advantage of CV Mnemonic code for confirmation of numeric codes this way is that common errors associated with numeric entry is less likely to occur. For example, repeating digits is less of a problem as repeating digits do not lead to repeating CV sequences. CV sequences do not have repeating sequences of single characters. Consider the code '7778 8886 6133 3441,' which contains several repeating digits. Using the CV Mnemonic balanced scheme, the above number is encoded as 'TITO WOVE QEJO SECI,' containing no repeating characters and less prone to human errors. Even though this approach is superior to the one where the user has to type the numeric code twice since, this approach can be cumbersome to the user. A second approach for error checking involves having a system instantaneously generates and displays the CV Mnemonic code as the user types the code. This helps users to observe if an error is being committed as well as spot the location of errors as they type the code (Figure 1).

USE OF CV MNEMONICS IN PAYMENT CARDS

In a survey to understand the difference in preference for numeric code and the CV Mnemonic, we provided 16 participants who are master workers on MTurk (age>55) with an image of a card with a 16-digit sequence of numeric digits or alphabetic characters (Figure 6). All participants were shown ten images, five of which displayed numeric codes, and the rest exhibited CV mnemonic codes equivalents of the numeric codes based on the canonical mapping scheme. The images were randomly assigned to the participants. The participants were asked to enter the codes into the text input box.

Figure 6: Images in Exploratory Study

At the end of the study, participants were asked, “Which of the two types of codes did you find easier to enter - numeric (such as ‘5370 6566 4104 9132’) or alphabetic (such as 'RINO HOJO CIGA PUQE’)?” Of all the participants, 43.75% stated a preference for CV Mnemonic and 56.25% stated a preference for the numeric code. One unexpected observation was that the relatively younger participants (age: 50-59) in the group preferred the CV Mnemonic, and the older users (age: 60-69) preferred the numeric code. One explanation could be that older users might have found it easier to type numeric codes.

Table 6. Preference for CV Mnemonic versus Numeric Code

Age	Prefer CV	Prefer Numeric
50-59	4/5 (80%)	1/5 (20%)
60-69	3/11 (27.27%)	8/11 (72.72%)

All Participants	7 /16 (43.75 %)	9/16 (56.25%)
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This study suggests heterogenous preference for users. It also suggests, that instead of replacing the existing numeric codes, the mnemonic could be provided alongside the numeric code. Payment systems may be designed to recognize both forms of code.

CV MNEMONIC COMPARED TO OTHER MNEMONIC METHODS

The most popular mnemonic method for numbers is the phonetic mnemonic (or mnemonic major) system developed by Gregor von Feinaigle (1760-1819), a former Cistercian monk (Bellezza et al. 1992). The phonetic mnemonic system consists of replacing each digit with a consonant sound, with vowels being added to make words (Bruce and Clemons 1982; Morris and Greer 1983). The consonants were chosen based on their resemblance to the numbers, 1 was represented by t, n, with two strokes to 2, and m, with three strokes, was related to 3 by Feinaigle. Worthen and Hunt (2011), reviewing the extant evidence, concludes that the most well-known mnemonic method for numbers, the phonetic method, may not be suitable for typical users. Moreover, the mnemonic representation obtained by applying the phonetic mnemonic method is not a parsimonious representation for the underlying numeric code. The phonetic method to encode numbers requires more characters than numbers, given that vowels are used only in aiding recall and do not carry numerical associations. Additionally, the users may struggle to create mnemonics since there is no well-defined mapping between the codes and pronounceable words.

Another well-known mnemonic technique is that of the telephone mnemonic used as part of 1800 vanity numbers (Horky 1995). In this technique, a telephone number key is associated with three or four alphabetic characters. This mnemonic approach allows specific numbers (but not all) to be transformed into memorable words. The third method is the table-index method, which links a number to a unique word in a lookup table. Each of the above common mnemonic approaches has various limitations that make them unsuitable as a general mnemonic system for numeric codes in digital environments. These limitations can be resolved partly through the method we describe, called CV Mnemonics.

In contrast to the phonetic mnemonic system, the number of characters required to represent the original number code is lower in the case of the CV mnemonic. For example, consider the four-digit code '445854' in the phonetic system; it is equivalent to the consonants RRLGLR. We can create a mnemonic by using filler vowels to yield a memorable code such as ROAR LEG LAIR. However, the process of generating such codes on the fly can be challenging for users, given that it may be cumbersome to generate memorable words given sequences of consonants. This task is particularly challenging for longer numeric codes (Worthen and Hunt 2011). Also, as demonstrated above, the number of characters is much higher than the underlying numeric code. In contrast, using the CV balanced mapping, we get the alphabetic code, LUPONU, a pronounceable word. In contrast to the phoneword mnemonic, the CV mnemonic consists of a one-to-many mapping from numbers to combinations of consonants and vowels. That is, each two-digit code is uniquely associated with a CV combination. Thus, in contrast to the phone word method, every numeric code yields a unique, pronounceable CV mnemonic code.

LIMITATIONS OF CV MNEMONIC

There are two key limitations of the CV Mnemonic method over the phonetic method. First, the CV mnemonics characters may not cue the original numbers for the balanced mapping scheme. This limitation can be addressed by creating a different mapping scheme, similar to the digit-consonant associations of phonetic mnemonic method (Bellezza 1996, p. 352; Fiorentini et

al. 2017), where the appearance of the consonant character cues the first digit of the 2-digit numeric code. We have used the phonetic mnemonic method as the basis for the selection of the consonants, and provide mnemonic aids (Table 7) similar to the ones described by Bellezza (1996). The *phonetic mapping* scheme based on the above associations is shown in Table 4.

Table 7: Mnemonic Aids based on Bellezza (1996)

Digit	Consonants	Vowel	Mnemonic aid for Consonants
0	S, Z	A	Z is the first sound in zero
1	D, T	E	D, T have one vertical stroke
2	H, N	I	H, N have two vertical strokes
3	M, W	O	M, W appear like a rotated 3
4	Q, R	U	Quad- begin with Q, 4 ends with the sound R
5	L, Y	A	L is Roman Numeral for 50, Y is the 25 th letter
6	G, J	E	G looks like a 6, J looks like the mirror image of 6
7	C, K	I	C is open like a 7, K is made up of two 7s
8	F, V	O	8 looks like a lowercase F
9	B, P	U	Lowercase B, P resembles rotated images of 6

Table 8: Phonetic Mapping for CV Mnemonic

00 SA	01 SE	02 SI	03 SO	04 SU	05 ZA	06 ZE	07 ZI	08 ZO	09 ZU
10 DA	11 DE	12 DI	13 DO	14 DU	15 TA	16 TE	17 TI	18 TO	19 TU
20 HA	21 HE	22 HI	23 HO	24 HU	25 NA	26 NE	27 NI	28 NO	29 NU
30 MA	31 ME	32 MI	33 MO	34 MU	35 WA	36 WE	37 WI	38 WO	39 WU
40 QA	41 QE	42 QI	43 QO	44 QU	45 RA	46 RE	47 RI	48 RO	49 RU
50 LA	51 LE	52 LI	53 LO	54 LU	55 YA	56 YE	57 YI	58 YO	59 YU
60 GA	61 GE	62 GI	63 GO	64 GU	65 JA	66 JE	67 JI	68 JO	69 JU
70 CA	71 CE	72 CI	73 CO	74 CU	75 KA	76 KE	77 KI	78 KO	79 KU
80 FA	81 FE	82 FI	83 FO	84 FU	85 VA	86 VE	87 VI	88 VO	89 VU
90 BA	91 BE	92 BI	93 BO	94 BU	95 PA	96 PE	97 PI	98 PO	99 PU

A second limitation is that while CV Mnemonic codes are pronounceable, they don't evoke concrete concepts, and may be ineffective for longer terms storage. To address this limitation, we present an extension of the CV Mnemonic method, where each CV combination is associated with three-letter English words that begin with the CV combination, and can cue concrete imagery (Table 9).⁹

Table 9: Three-character Representative Concrete Imagery Words for CV Combinations

00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09
BAT	BED	BIB	BOA	BUG	CAR	CEE	CID	COW	CUP
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
DAM	DEN	DIG	DOG	DUG	FAN	FEE	FIG	FOX	FUR
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
GAL	GEM	GIN	GOO	GUM	HAM	HEN	HIP	HOE	HUT

⁹ Such imagery is often bizarre which makes it potentially more memorable.

30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39
JAR	JET	JIG	JOG	JUG	KAB	KEY	KID	KOA	KUE
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49
LAB	LEG	LID	LOG	LUG	MAP	MEN	MIX	MOP	MUD
50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59
NAP	NET	NIP	NOD	NUN	PAN	PEG	PIG	POT	PUB
60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69
QAT	QUE	QIN	QUO	QUA	RAT	RED	RIB	ROD	RUM
70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79
SAX	SEA	SIT	SOY	SUN	TAR	TEA	TIN	TOE	TUX
80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89
VAN	VET	VIA	VOW	VUG	WAX	WET	WIG	WOK	WUD
90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99
YAM	YEN	YIN	YOU	YUG	ZAP	ZEN	ZIT	ZOO	ZUZ

To identify concrete imagery words, we began with the 2019 Collins scrabble word list which contained 279,496 words.¹⁰ Using the doc2concrete R library (Yeomans 2021), we estimated the concreteness of all three-letter words that begin with consonant-vowel combinations. For each CV combination, we selected the words with highest level of concreteness. Concreteness values could not be identified for some CV combinations. No three-letter words that begin with QO, and QE were not found, and were instead substituted with words QUE, and QUO.

In Table 9 we list the selected three-character words that begin with each CV combination. For example, using the table we find that six-digit number such as ‘678087’ that has a CV equivalent of ‘RIVAWI’ is associated with an ordered sequence of imagery words RIB, VAN, and WIG. Using this approach, we can create synthetic compound words that can engender concrete but bizarre mental imagery (Einstein et al. 1989; Riefer and Rouder 1992), such as ‘LUG-POT’ (4458) and ‘GUM-HAM-ZOO’ (242598). The payment card number ‘4000 1234 5678 9010’ can be encoded using the ordered list of words ‘LAB-BAT’, ‘DIG-JUG’, ‘PEG-TOE’ and ‘YAM-DAM’, which may be easier to memorize than the original code. Similarly, 4-character picture words can be generated, which allows for the possibility of a larger number of imagery words to choose from (Table 10). These 4-character words can be used to generate imagery (Figure 7) as well as to generate imagery words where digits repeat, such as YEN-YELL for 9191.

Table 10: Four-character Representative Concrete Imagery Words for CV Combinations

00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09
BALL	BEAN	BIRD	BOOT	BULB	CAGE	CELL	CLIP	COMB	CUBE
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
DART	DESK	DISH	DOLL	DRUM	FACE	FERN	FISH	FROG	FUEL
20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
GATE	GEAR	GIFT	GOLD	GLUE	HAIR	HERB	HILL	HORN	HUSK
30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39
JAIL	JEAN	JIVE	JOKE	JURY	KALE	KNEE	KITE	KNOT	KUDO
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49
LAMP	LEAF	LIME	LOCK	LUNG	MASK	MENU	MILK	MOON	MULE
50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59
NAIL	NEST	NICE	NOSE	NUKE	PAGE	PEEL	PIPE	POND	PLUS
60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69
QUAD	QUEY	QUIZ	QUOD	QUUX	RAFT	REED	RING	ROBE	RUBY
70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79
SAND	SLED	SHIP	SOCK	SUIT	TAIL	TREE	TIRE	TOOL	TUBE
80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89
VASE	VENT	VINE	VOTE	VUGG	WAVE	WELL	WIRE	WORM	WUSS
90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99

¹⁰ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/scrabble>

YARN	YELL	YIRD	YOYO	YUKA	ZARF	ZEAL	ZING	ZOOM	ZUPA
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Figure 7: CV Mnemonic Imagery Words

DISCUSSION

Given the increased use of numeric codes in digital environments, users might benefit from encoding such codes in a more memorable way using mnemonic techniques. This paper describes an easy-to-use mnemonic method, the CV Mnemonic, for encoding numerical codes as alphabetic character sequences made up of consonant-vowel pairs to improve the usability of digital interfaces. This approach has several advantages over the most common mnemonic schemes for numbers, such as the phonetic method, the phoneword mnemonic, and the table-index method. In particular, we consider the CV Mnemonic to be helpful in memorizing, recognizing, and verifying random machine-generated numeric codes such as PINs, bank account numbers and encryption keys. We illustrate how CV Mnemonic can improve digital usability in the context of payment cards, two-factor authentication schemes, and passwords.

CV Mnemonics can be potentially used to encode numeric codes to improve memorability in many situations where the use of numeric codes hamper usability. If our objective is to improve short-term recall of the code, the CV Mnemonic may be used directly. If the situation calls for long-term recall, it may be necessary to encode CV Mnemonic as picture words.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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